

THE PROCESS OF DESIGNING TEACHING MATERIALS FOR ENGLISH FOR SPECIFIC PURPOSES (ESP) COURSES IN THE FIELD OF MEDICINE. THE IMPORTANCE OF CONDUCTING A DETAILED NEEDS ANALYSIS.

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Annotation: *The article discusses the process of designing teaching materials for English for Specific Purposes (ESP) courses in the field of medicine. It emphasizes the importance of conducting a detailed needs analysis prior to constructing training materials. The needs analysis is divided into four parts: inquiries about objectives, motivation, and personal interests; an exam to assess English proficiency in medicine; a brief essay about students' expectations for the course's conclusion; and focus group discussions with medical students. Each part is described along with instructions and justifications for its implementation.*

Key words: *Designing teaching materials, English for Specific Purposes (ESP), Needs analysis, OET test, Focus group discussions.*

Annotatsiya: *Maqolada tibbiyot sohasidagi Ingliz tilining maxsus maqsadlarda (ESP) kurslari uchun o'quv materiallarini loyihalash jarayoni muhokama qilinadi. U o'quv materiallarini yaratishdan oldin batafsil ehtiyoj tahlilini o'tkazish muhimligini ta'kidlaydi. Ehtiyojlarni tahlil qilish to'rt qismga bo'linadi: maqsadlar, motivatsiya va shaxsiy manfaatlar haqidagi so'rovlar; tibbiyotda ingliz tilini bilish darajasini baholash uchun imtihon; talabalarning kurs yakunidan umidlari haqida qisqacha insho; va tibbiyot talabalari bilan fokus-guruh muhokamalari. Har bir qism ko'rsatmalar va uni amalga oshirish uchun asoslar bilan tavsiflanadi.*

Kalit so'zlar: *O'quv materiallarini loyihalash, Maxsus maqsadlar uchun ingliz tili (ESP), Ehtiyojlarni tahlil qilish, OET testi, Fokus-guruh muhokamalari.*

Аннотация: *В статье рассматривается процесс разработки учебных материалов для курсов английского языка для специальных целей (ESP) в сфере*

медицины. В нем подчеркивается важность проведения детального анализа потребностей до разработки учебных материалов. Анализ потребностей разделен на четыре части: вопросы о целях, мотивации и личных интересах; экзамен для оценки уровня владения английским языком в области медицины; краткое эссе об ожиданиях студентов от завершения курса; и дискуссии в фокус-группах со студентами-медиками. Каждая часть описана вместе с инструкциями и обоснованиями по ее выполнению.

Ключевые слова: разработка учебных материалов, английский для специальных целей (ESP), анализ потребностей, тест OET, обсуждения в фокус-группах.

The process of choosing, customizing, and assessing instruction based on a set of terms of reference is known as designing teaching material. Prior to constructing training materials, need analysis is crucial for English for Specific Purpose (Saragih, 2014)

In order to make detailed and precise needs analysis, it was decided to conduct it in four parts:

1. Inquiries about objectives, motivation, and personal interests
2. The exam to ascertain English proficiency in the field of medicine.
3. Brief essay about the students' expectations
4. Conducting focus group discussions with medical students

Part 1:

Instructions:

In order to develop a relationship with the instructor and show that their needs are being taken into consideration, students should pick the topics they believe are most essential to discuss. This will help them feel heard. The results of the survey will be gathered, and the program will cover and pay particular attention to the topics that were most commonly chosen.

Please, tick the statements below that particularly interest you:

- Developing medical vocabulary and terminology in English

- Improving communication skills with patients and colleagues in English
- Enhancing writing skills for medical reports and research papers
- Practicing English for medical presentations and conferences
- Strengthening listening and speaking skills for patient interviews and case discussions
- Understanding and navigating English medical literature and resources
- Cultural competence and cross-cultural communication in a medical context
- Preparing for international medical opportunities and collaborations
- Gaining confidence in using English in medical settings
- Other (please specify)
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Justifications: Universities must look for and adopt new techniques and technologies that provide them a competitive edge in the market for educational services as a result of contemporary trends in the growth of the economy and higher education. The creation and execution of efficient education quality management systems is one of the most powerful tools for inspiring potential customers with trust in the caliber of educational services offered by the institution.

Since students are both the primary "costumers" and active participants in the instructional activities of the university, Mingazov concluded that a student survey might be one of the most useful instruments for evaluating a university (2009, p-17). It is possible to rank various factors according to the degree of their influence on the quality of the educational process, identify the most difficult areas, and direct the university's main efforts and resources (material, technical, methodological, information, etc.) to improve their activities, as well as to determine the true quality of educational services provided by a given educational institution.

Part 2:

We made the decision to use the OET test content as the exam. The key advantages are further discussed in the reasoning.

OET is an international English language exam that evaluates a healthcare professional's level of language ability before allowing them to register and work in an English-speaking setting. It offers a verified, trustworthy evaluation of each of the four language skills—listening, reading, writing, and speaking—with a focus on communicating in front of a professional audience in the medical field.

Dentistry, dietetics, medicine, nursing, Occupational Therapy, optometry, pharmacy, physiotherapy, podiatry, radiography, speech pathology, and veterinary science are among the 12 health professions that the OET evaluates. Our kids will find this exam intriguing because they haven't chosen a career yet.

OET evaluates speaking, reading, writing, and listening skills. Every skill area has a different subtest. The Reading and Listening subtests are intended to evaluate a student's comprehension of spoken and written English in situations pertaining to general health and medicine. All occupations must pass the Listening and Reading subtests. Each profession-specific Writing and Speaking subtest is created to measure a candidate's proficiency in English in the relevant professional environment.

Note the information is retrieved from oet.com*

Test description:

Sub-test (duration)	Content	Shows candidates can:
Listening (45 minutes)	3 tasks Common to all 12 professions	follow and understand a range of health-related spoken materials such as patient consultations and lectures.
Reading (60 minutes)	3 tasks Common to all 12 professions	read and understand different types of text on health-related subjects.
Writing (45 minutes)	1 task Specific to each profession	write a letter in a clear and accurate way which is relevant for the reader.
Speaking (20 minutes)	2 tasks Specific to each profession	effectively communicate in a real-life context through the use of role plays.

Justification: The diagnostic of knowledge and skills, as well as the monitoring of the degree of required learning outcomes, receive a lot of attention in the context of a contemporary school. Since learning is an individual process, mechanisms of control are necessary to provide for verification:

First, the extent to which each student has met the requirements for training; second, the depth to which educational abilities have been developed; and third, the capacity to apply newly acquired information in contexts other than those required by the learning goals.

With the potential for machine entry of data (answers) and automated processing of the result with specified quality requirements, testing is used to swiftly assess the level of students' knowledge. Despite its drawbacks, test technology offers a quick and accurate means to assess a student's level of preparation by having them complete straightforward activities, select an option for the answer, or add words, formulae, or other terminology.

Part 3:

Students will be given forty minutes to write this essay.

Essay: Expectations for the Course's Conclusion

Please write a brief essay (200-300 words) about your expectations for the conclusion of the ESP course. What specific goals or outcomes would you like to achieve by the end of the course?

Justification: The distinctive ways that contemporary adolescents perceive information must also be taken into account in order to improve the efficacy of the educational process. According to E. Toffler (2022), people have a "clip" view of information, which means they see it as instantaneous frames and split up chunks. As a result, pupils are unsure of what to anticipate. This essay will assist in putting everything in its proper perspective and it will also detail the standards for pupils. It will be feasible to evaluate whether we were successful in meeting their expectations at the conclusion of the course.

Part 4:

Students will discuss their expectations with us in order to share their opinions with the class and get new ideas from classmates. This is done at the very end so that each other's opinions do not affect their answers in questionnaires and essays.

Focus Group Discussions with Medical Students

During the focus group discussions, we will explore topics such as:

1. Your experiences with English in a medical setting
2. Areas where you feel you need further language support
3. Any challenges you face in effectively communicating in English.

Note: The information gathered will help us develop a comprehensive understanding of your needs and design a curriculum that meets those needs effectively.

Needs Analysis Report

This report presents the findings of a needs analysis conducted to understand the language needs, lacks, and wants of medical students in Uzbekistan, with a focus on their English language skills and communication tasks within a medical context. The analysis aimed to gather insights that would inform the development of an effective English for Specific Purposes (ESP) course tailored to the needs of the students.

Methods: To gather the necessary information, several methods were employed, including an objective, motivation, and personal interest survey, an English proficiency exam, and focus group discussions with a representative sample of medical students.

Findings:

Language Needs and Objectives: The survey results revealed that the majority of students expressed a need to develop medical vocabulary and terminology in English. They also expressed a strong interest in improving their communication skills with patients and colleagues, including conducting patient interviews and engaging in case discussions. Additionally, students expressed a desire to enhance their writing skills for medical reports and research papers.

Exam results: The ability to speak a foreign language, particularly English, is currently considered to be one of the essential qualities of a highly trained professional in the era of globalization and the creation of a single information space. The ensuing descriptions of almost every scientific discovery made in the world are written in English. Unfortunately, the results showed that despite a good level of general English, students lack even the most basic knowledge of medical English. They are completely unaware of the terms associated with diagnosis, treatment, diseases and medical instruments. Only about 20 percent of the students were able to cope with the tasks given by us at least a little. This shows that we need to start with the basics and the simplest tasks, such as symptom interviews, doctor's prescriptions, and so on.

Specific Skills and Tasks: The focus group discussions further highlighted specific language skills and communication tasks that the students perceived as essential. These included:

- Delivering effective presentations in English for medical conferences.
- Strengthening listening and speaking skills for patient interviews and discussions with colleagues.
- Navigating and comprehending English medical literature and resources.
- Developing cultural competence and cross-cultural communication in a medical context.

Motivation and Personal Interests: The survey responses also indicated that students were motivated by the prospect of preparing for international medical opportunities and collaborations. They expressed a strong desire to gain confidence

in using English within medical settings and were open to exploring additional areas of interest that could be integrated into the curriculum.

Based on the needs analysis, it is evident that medical students in Uzbekistan have a strong motivation to develop their English language skills within a medical context. The findings indicate a high demand for targeted instruction in medical vocabulary, communication skills, writing skills, and cultural competence. Additionally, students expressed a keen interest in international medical opportunities and collaboration.

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